

Analysis of the Factors Militating Against the Performance of the Federal Government Sites and Services Scheme in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

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Abstract

Site and Services Scheme entails public financial commitment for land acquisition, planning, design and installation of basic infrastructure, such as paved roads, water and electricity before the sites are allocated on leasehold basis to the public for housing development. The Federal Government of Nigeria introduced the Sites and Services Scheme in 1986 as a viable means of increasing supply of serviced plots at affordable costs in order to achieve housing delivery. The concept was adopted and first domesticated in Nigeria by the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing in 1986. The underlying principle of Site and Services Scheme is that the authorities would provide the land and the infrastructural facilities, while the individual allottees proceed to build their houses in accordance with the approved building plan. The aim of this study is to analyse the factors militating against the performance of the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The objectives are: to classify/determine the extent of completion/ development/services of the various Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South, Nigeria, to assess the implementation of the Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South-South, Nigeria, to identify/determine the critical factors affecting the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South Nigeria and to develop a guideline for improving the implementation of the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South, Nigeria. To achieve the objectives of the study, questionnaires backed with interviews were used to elicit information from 208 respondents comprising, Land officers, Estate Officers, Town Planners, Surveyors, Architects, Builders, Civil Engineers, Structural Engineers and Quantity Surveyors. These respondents are real estate professional staff of the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development in South-South, Nigeria. The total population of the study (208) was adopted as the sample size. Descriptive statistical tools comprising tables, mean, variance and standard deviation were used in the data presentation and analysis. Inferential statistical tools were used to draw conclusions from data. The statistical technique used in testing the hypothesis is one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The findings reveal that the Federal Government sites and services scheme in South-South Nigeria is yet to effectively achieve or realize its prime objectives due to the following reasons: Poor funding/budgetary constraints, Delay in payment of compensation, encroachment of sites, Poor location of sites, fraudulent/double allocation of plots, conflicts with State Government, Inter-Departmental Conflicts, Inadequate Manpower, among others. The study recommends adequate funding of Site and Services Scheme to ensure timely provision of infrastructure and well-equipped site monitoring and development control team for effective control and performance of the scheme.

Keywords: Factors, Militating, Performance, Government Sites, Services Scheme

Introduction

Housing is an important component of human settlement which renders tremendous service to humanity thereby serving as an important and indispensable element of human settlement. There has been an increasing awareness in both the developed and developing nations, since the last three decades on the need to provide more housing to rapidly growing population (Alhassan et al, 2017).

However, the adequate provision of this basic need in the face of rapid urbanization of the population in Nigeria goes unabated, reaching a highest peak in the urban center. This phenomenal growth rate among urban population in Nigeria has contributed to scarcity of the housing stock in most urban centers which in turn results to overcrowding, slum condition and development of squatter's shacks (Adeniyi, 1974). Coupled with this ugly development is the growing deterioration of the housing environment. The situation becomes so unbearable that many residential environments result to unhealthy human habitation, especially that of the low income group. And more so, is the lack of adequate financial and personnel resources to develop land on such a scale as would meet the demand of the teeming population (Alhassan et al, 2017).

According to Olayinwola, et al (2005), the synthesis of government activities has shown that during the past few years, a number of constructive programmes and far reaching actions have been taken by the Federal Government of Nigeria to address the increasing housing needs of the people.

One of such innovative schemes which has received wide acknowledgement and following has been the "Sites-and-Services Schemes" (Aribigbola and Ayeniyo, 2012).

Site and Services Schemes approach is identified in the nation's National Housing Policy (1991 and 2011) as one of the key strategies to enhance housing provision in Nigeria, and is expected to be adopted by the Local, State and Federal levels of government in the country. Site and Services Scheme, in the opinion of Srinivas (2011), entails provision of plots of land, either on ownership or land lease tenure, along with a bare minimum of essential infrastructure needed for habitation.

Two major variants of this approach existing are: provision of an empty plot of land and some services (like water, electricity and sanitation connections); and, the provision of a "core" house (consisting of a toilet and kitchen only) on the plot of land with attached services.

Site and services approach was readily embraced by every tier of government in Nigeria, and plots of land of various sizes have been compulsorily acquired for site and services schemes in every nook and crannies of the nation (Sanni and Afolayan, 2014).

Consequently, the Federal Government of Nigeria through its agency, Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, adopted the Sites and Services Scheme in 1986 as a viable

means of increasing supply of serviced plots at affordable costs in order to achieve sustainable housing delivery (Mikail, 2018).

However, the implementation of the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme has been ongoing for a long time now but there seems not to be much progress, indicating that a critical gap exists between the programme's target and reality.

Against this backdrop, this research paper aims at analysing the critical factors affecting the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria, with a view of proffering solutions that will enhance the performance of the scheme.

Concept of Site and Services Scheme

The concept of sites and services scheme has been implemented through the World Bank assistance, for about two decades in many developing countries. It entails the provision of plots of land (or sites) with infrastructure on it (or services) of which the beneficiaries have to, in most of the schemes build their own houses, ranging from the subdivided plots only to a serviced plots of land with a "core" house built on it (Srinivas, 2011). The concept, in principle, focuses directly on lower income groups and it attempts to deliver shelter and services at a cost they can afford while still ensuring that the costs of sites-and-services project are recovered so that the project can be replicated. To Mayo and Gross (1987), sites and services is a: "government sponsored package of shelter related services which range from a minimal level of 'surveyed plot' to an intermediate level of 'services sites' to an upper level of 'core housing' complete with utilities and access to community-based services. The level of services depends on the ability and willingness of beneficiary populations to afford them". Three important considerations central to the concept of sites and services are:

- (1) The projects must provide a package of benefits that is widely acceptable and affordable by the beneficiaries; the charges must be small mortgage repayments not generally exceeding 20% of the income of participants;
- (2) The cost of the project must, to a great extent, be recoverable; and
- (3) The programme must be capable of being replicated to meet the demands of others for urban housing and community services (Onibokun, et al, 1989).

So, site(s)-and-service(s) schemes evolved out of two quite different lines of thought. The first one emphasizes the labour input of the allottee, participation in the form of self-help construction. The allottee builds the house according to a design prepared by the housing agency, so that it meets all the standards, but is more affordable for a low-income family. The second line of thought emphasizes freedom to build: the dweller is in full control of the

construction process and can construct the house according to his or her needs and priorities, resources and abilities without being constraint by externally imposed standards (progressive development) (Yap,1998).

The central concept of the sites-and-services scheme is a shift of focus from the provision of a complete house to the provision of a serviced plot and the delegation of the responsibility for the construction of the house to the allottee (Pealtic, 1982). The purest form of a sites-and-services scheme is an urban residential land subdivision where the developer sells or leases serviced plots, i.e. land with basic infrastructure (roads, water supply, drainage, a human waste disposal system, electricity) to a specific target group: low-income households. The infrastructure may be available on the plot or be shared by a number of households. The allottee is responsible for the construction of the house for which the project extends loans. The beneficiaries usually have to meet definite criteria: they should fall in a particular income bracket and have a regular income or a fixed employment to ensure loan recovery; they cannot own any other urban property and they must have lived in the city for an extended period to prevent the schemes from becoming magnets for rural migrants (Yap,1998).

Research Methodology

Field Survey was adopted as the research design for the study. The study adopted both Primary and Secondary sources of data collection.

Primary data was collected through the use of oral interview and questionnaires designed specifically for the study. Secondary data were collected through text books, journals, internet sources, official publications, official gazettes, information from the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development etc.

The study population for this study comprised of 208 respondents from the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development in South-South, Nigeria which consists of 32 Land officers, 23 Estate Officers, 31 Town Planners, 28 Surveyors, 20 Architects, 17 Builders, 21 Civil Engineers, 18 Structural Engineers and 18 Quantity Surveyors. The total population of the study (208) was adopted as the sample size since it is a manageable size.

Descriptive statistical tools comprising tables, mean, variance and standard deviation were used in the data presentation and analysis. Inferential statistical tools were used to draw conclusions from data. The statistical technique used in testing the hypothesis is one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Results

A. Extent of Completion

The likert scales used for the extent of completion of the sites and services scheme are 0–20 percent completed (0.00–1.00); 21–40 percent completed (1.01–2.00); 41–60 percent completed (2.01–3.00); 61–80 percent completed (3.01–4.00); 81–100 percent completed (4.01–5.00). The responses of the respondents are presented in tables 1.

Table 1: Extent of Completion of the sites and services scheme in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	State	FG. SSS	Mean	Remark
1	Akwa Ibom	Mbierebe Obio	1.40	21–40 percent completed
		Ikot Abasi	2.80	41–60 percent completed
		Eket	3.00	41–60 percent completed
2	Bayelsa	Amarata-Onapa	3.20	61–80 percent completed
		Ekeki -Yenegoa	3.00	41–60 percent completed
		Nembe	2.00	21–40 percent completed
		Ekeremor	2.00	21–40 percent completed
3	Cross River	University satellite town Calabar	4.20	81–100 percent completed
		Ikot Ene Obong, Calabar	2.40	41–60 percent completed
4	Delta	Agbor	1.80	21–40 percent completed
		Asaba Extension	4.80	81–100 percent completed
		Kwali	1.60	21–40 percent completed
5	Edo	Egba–Abraka	1.20	21–40 percent completed
		Ugbowo Benin City	2.20	41–60 percent completed
6	Rivers	Borikiri	4.20	81–100 percent completed
		Woji	5.00	81–100 percent completed
		Rumueme	4.80	81–100 percent completed
		Rumudomaya	4.00	61–80 percent completed

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025

B. Extent of Development

The likert scales used for the extent of development of the sites and services scheme are: Not at all developed (0.00–1.00); somewhat developed (1.01–2.00); moderately developed (2.01–

3.00); mostly developed (3.01–4.00); fully developed (4.01–5.00). The results are presented in table 1a below.

Table 1a: Extent of Development of the sites and services scheme in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	State	FG. SSS	Mean	Remark
1	Akwa Ibom	Mbierebe Obio	1.40	somewhat developed
		Ikot Abasi	2.80	moderately developed
		Eket	3.00	moderately developed
2	Bayelsa	Amarata-Onapa	3.00	moderately developed
		Ekeki -Yenegoa	3.00	moderately developed
		Nembe	2.00	somewhat developed
		Ekeremor	2.00	somewhat developed
3	Cross River	University satellite town Calabar	3.80	mostly developed
		Ikot Ene Obong, Calabar	2.60	moderately developed
4	Delta	Agbor	1.80	somewhat developed
		Asaba Extension	4.80	fully developed
		Kwali	2.20	moderately developed
5	Edo	Egba–Abraka	1.20	somewhat developed
		Ugbowo Benin City	2.20	moderately developed
6	Rivers	Borikiri	4.00	mostly developed
		Woji	4.80	fully developed
		Rumueme	5.00	fully developed
		Rumudomaya	4.00	mostly developed

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025

C. Availability of Services

The likert scales used here are strongly disagree=1; disagree=2; no opinion=3; disagree=4; strongly disagree=5. Mean cutoff was obtained from the likert scales as follows:

$$x = \frac{1+2+3+4+5}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$$

From this, mean of greater than or equal to 3.0 implies agree while mean less than 3.0 implies disagree.

Table 1b: Availability of Services in the sites and services schemes

S/N	Item	AIS	BS	CRS	DS	ES	RS
1	Presence of basic facilities	1.8	3.6	4.0	3.8	2.8	4.2
2	Availability of infrastructural serviced plots	1.8	2.4	2.4	3.0	2.0	4.0
3	Presence of good access roads	1.8	3.6	4.0	3.8	3.6	4.0
4	Proper drainage systems	1.8	2.4	4.0	3.8	2.8	4.0
5	Portable water supply	3.6	4.0	4.0	3.8	3.2	4.2
6	Availability of good sewage systems	2.8	3.6	4.0	3.6	3.2	4.2
7	Constant electricity	1.8	3.0	2.0	2.6	1.8	3.8
8	Availability of security services	3.2	4.0	4.0	3.8	3.0	4.2
9	Availability of individual (private) services	3.2	4.0	3.6	3.8	3.2	4.0
10	Availability of community services	1.8	3.6	4.0	3.8	2.8	4.2

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025

Key for Implementation: Not at all implemented (NI=0.00–1.00); somewhat implemented (SI=1.01–2.00); mostly implemented (MI=2.01–3.00); largely implemented (LI=3.01–4.00); fully implemented (FI=4.01–5.00).

Key for Effectiveness: Not at all effective (NE=0.00–1.00); somewhat effective (SE=1.01–2.00); mostly effective (ME=2.01–3.00); largely effective (LE=3.01–4.00); fully effective (FE=4.01–5.00).

Table 2: Implementation and effectiveness of the Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	Item	AIS	BS	CRS	DS	ES	RS
Assessment of Implementation							
1	Infrastructure Development and Service Provision	1.6	2.2	2	2.4	1.8	3.6
2	Land Accessibility and Allocation Efficiency	2.2	2.6	2.2	2.6	2	3.5
3	Housing Development and Occupancy Rate	1.6	2.6	2.4	2.6	2	3.5
4	Socio-Economic Impact	1.6	2.4	2.4	2.6	2	3
5	Affordability for Low- and Middle-Income Groups	1.6	2	2	2.4	1.4	3
6	Environmental and Sustainability Considerations	1.6	2	2	2.6	1.8	3
7	Policy and Governance Efficiency	1.6	2.2	2	2.6	2	3

8	Beneficiary Satisfaction and Feedback	1.6	2	2	2.4	1.8	3
Mean		1.68	2.25	2.13	2.53	1.85	3.2
Remark		SI	MI	MI	MI	SI	LI
Assessment of Effectiveness							
9	Infrastructure Development and Service Provision	1.6	2.6	2.2	2.6	1.8	4
10	Land Accessibility and Allocation Efficiency	1.6	2.6	2.4	2.8	1.8	3.75
11	Housing Development and Occupancy Rate	1.6	2.6	2.4	2.8	2	4
12	Socio-Economic Impact	1.6	2.2	2.2	2.8	1.8	3.4
13	Affordability for Low- and Middle-Income Groups	1.6	2	2	2.4	1.4	3
14	Environmental and Sustainability Considerations	1.6	2.2	2	2.8	1.8	3.25
15	Policy and Governance Efficiency	1.6	2	2.2	2.8	1.8	3.25
16	Beneficiary Satisfaction and Feedback	1.6	2.4	2	2.4	1.8	3.25
Mean		1.60	2.33	2.18	2.68	1.78	3.49
Remark		SE	ME	ME	ME	SE	LE

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025

Table 3: Critical factors affecting the Federal Government Site and Services Schemes

S/N	Item	AIS	BS	CRS	DS	ES	RS
1	Funding and budgetary allocations	4.4	4.6	4.2	3.6	4.6	3.6
2	Inflation and cost of construction	4.2	4.0	3.6	3.6	3.6	2.8
3	Land Values and market demand	2.6	2.2	2.0	2.4	3.6	2.8
4	Land Tenure and ownership laws	3.0	2.0	2.8	2.8	3.0	2.0
5	Regulatory approvals	2.6	2.2	2.6	2.6	3.2	1.8
6	Zoning and urban planning laws	2.6	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.0	1.8
7	Availability of basic infrastructure	4.6	4.0	4.0	3.6	4.0	4.0
8	Cost of infrastructure development	4.4	4.0	4.0	3.6	3.6	4.0
9	Maintenance and sustainability	3.8	2.4	3.6	2.8	2.6	3.2
10	Population Growth and housing demand	4.2	3.4	3.6	3.6	3.4	4.0
11	Affordability and accessibility	3.8	3.0	4.0	3.6	4.0	3.0
12	Resettlement and displacement issues	4.4	4.4	4.0	3.6	4.4	4.0
13	Government Commitment and political will	4.2	3.4	4.0	3.0	4.0	4.0
14	Corruption and mismanagement	4.0	3.0	3.8	3.2	3.6	3.8
15	Public Private Partnerships (PPP)	3.0	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.0	2.0

16	Land suitability and topography	3.8	4.4	4.0	2.4	3.6	3.2
17	Environmental impact	3.2	4.0	2.6	2.4	2.8	3.8
18	Litigations on available sites	4.2	4.2	4.0	3.6	4.0	2.8
19	Double/fraudulent allocations	4.2	4.2	4.0	3.6	4.0	4.0
20	Encroachment of available sites	4.2	4.2	4.0	3.6	4.0	3.6
21	Conflicts with State governments	4.2	4.2	4.0	3.6	4.0	3.6
22	Interdepartmental conflicts	3.8	4.2	4.0	3.6	4.0	4.0
23	Insecurity	3.6	4.0	3.8	3.2	3.6	2.2

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Table 4: Guideline for improving the implementation of federal site and services scheme in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	STAGES OF OPERATION	ACTIVITY
1.	Land Acquisition	There should be a proper acquisition of any land acquired for site and services scheme. All acquisitions should be gazette. Perfection and signing of exchange of letters should be properly documented. This is to ensure that all acquisitions are properly concluded.
2.	Payment of compensation	Prompt payment of compensation to original land owners/host community should be carried out after land acquisitions, so as to avoid Litigations and encroachments.
3.	Survey and Site Execution	There should be a detailed design and preparation of layout plans by the town planning unit. Perimeter, parcellation and topographical survey by the cadastral survey unit should be done timely. This will help in determination of flood lines for erosion control.
4.	Needs assessment	There should be soil analysis, feasibility studies and Environmental Impact Assessment on the land/site.
5.	Provision of infrastructure	There should be timely planning, design and commencement of provision of infrastructure to site by the engineering services unit.
6.	Allocation of serviced plots for housing development	Advertisement and allocation of serviced plots should be to only financial capable allottees who

		are willing to commence development to site on time.
7.	Public Private Partnership arrangement (PPP)	Where the Government fails to provide infrastructure due to budgetary constraints, Public Private Partnership arrangement (PPP) either by an individual or by allottees of schemes coming together under an umbrella association should be encouraged in the development of site and services scheme. This will go a long way in reducing the infrastructure burden on the Federal Government.
8.	Revocation of undeveloped plots	Any land that is not developed at a specific time should be revoked and reallocated to any individual that is ready to develop. This will curtail land speculation and encroachments.
9.	Monitoring and Control	There should be robust monitoring team to oversee scheme implementation, adherence to town planning laws, control of developments, maintenance of infrastructure and prevention of fraudulent activities on Federal Government lands.
10.	Capacity Building	There should be regular training and capacity-building programs for staff and stakeholders involved in the scheme implementation to enhance efficiency.

Presentation of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the extent of completion, extent of development and availability of services of the various Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Statistical Tool Used: One–way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Reason for the choice of Tool: Five levels of observations were compared.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, otherwise reject it.

Table 5: ANOVA for hypothesis one

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Extent of Completion	Between Groups	146.386	5	29.277	273.067	.000
	Within Groups	19.728	184	.107		
	Total	166.114	189			
Extent of Development	Between Groups	141.739	5	28.348	269.948	.000
	Within Groups	19.322	184	.105		
	Total	161.061	189			
Availability of Services	Between Groups	51.070	5	10.214	74.484	.000
	Within Groups	25.232	184	.137		
	Total	76.302	189			

Source: Researcher's Statistical Computation, 2025

From table 5, it can be seen that the p-values of extent of completion, extent of development and availability of services are all 0.000, which are less than 0.05. The implication is that there is significant difference between the extent of completion, extent of development and availability of services of the various Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. That is, the extent of completion, extent of development and availability of services significantly differ in the various states.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the level of implementation and effectiveness of the Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Statistical Tool Used: One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Reason for the choice of Tool: Five levels of observations were compared.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, otherwise reject it.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA for hypothesis two

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Assessment of Implementation	Between Groups	49.301	5	9.860	47.063	.000
	Within Groups	38.550	184	.210		
	Total	87.851	189			
Assessment of Effectiveness	Between Groups	74.138	5	14.828	69.488	.000
	Within Groups	39.262	184	.213		
	Total	113.400	189			

Source: Researcher's Statistical Computation, 2025

From table 6, it can be seen that the p-values of the assessment of implementation and effectiveness are both 0.000, which is less than 0.05. It means that there is significant difference between the level of implementation and effectiveness of the Federal Government Site and Services Schemes in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. It means that the levels of implementation and effectiveness of the FG SSS significantly vary across the south-south states.

Conclusion

This study has identified the critical factors militating against the performance of the Federal Government Sites and Services Schemes in South-South, Nigeria and equally developed a guideline that will enhance an effective and robust Site and Services Scheme. It is believed, however, that if the identified challenges are adequately addressed as per the solutions/recommendations, the programme will be a successful and credible alternative approach in reducing Nigerians housing deficit estimated to be about seventeen (17) million units (Oniemola, 2014).

Recommendations

After a critical examination of the Federal Government Site and Services Scheme in South-South Geopolitical zone of Nigeria, a number of strategic options were offered as recommendations. They include as follows:

- i. The Federal Government should take up whole or partial funding of provision of infrastructural facilities in Site and Services Scheme as a sure way of increasing the national housing stock and as a poverty eradication strategy. In this connection, the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development should mount a quiet campaign to convince the Federal Government to make budgetary provisions for housing infrastructure which should be seen principally as a social service to people.

Where allottees are expected to pay fully for, or make partial contribution to the funding for the provision of infrastructure to the Sites and Services Schemes, a case should be made by the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development to be allowed to

receive such payments into a **Special Projects Accounts** to enable ease of disbursement, though under strict guidelines and due process. This is to avoid a situation where such monies are received into **Consolidated Revenue Account** of the Federal Government and then becomes inaccessible, thereby frustrating the well-intentioned exercise.

A typical example is the successful massive infrastructural development of the Federal Capital Territory due to its withdrawal from the **Single Treasury Account (TSA)**.

- ii. Timely provision of infrastructure and prompt payment of compensation to the owners of acquired land/local land owning communities will go a long way in preventing resistance, threats and encroachment into Federal Government lands by land grabbers, militant youth groups, State Governments, among others. It will also encourage prompt development of houses by allottees of the scheme.
- iii. There is need to review the rates used in assessment of compensation payable on acquired land for site and services. Most times, the amount of compensation paid to the host communities/local land owning communities are too small for them to accept wholeheartedly.
- iv. There is need for the Federal Government to sensitize the State Government on the provisions of Sections 49(1) and 51(2) of the Land Use Act regarding Federal Government right to manage lands in the states. This will help in reducing the constant frictions/conflicts between the Federal and State Government.
- v. In order to curtail incessant double and fraudulent land allocations, there is need for computerization and creation of electronic database of Federal Government land records. This exercise has been going on for some time under the Federal Government Land Information System (FELIS). It is intended to save files/documents that are badly deteriorated, prevent further loss and host the data of all Federal Government land records within the country in a manner that would enable faster retrieval of data and decision making. The results have been less than satisfactory due to budgetary constraints and other challenges, but there is hope for improvement, especially if adequate funds are injected in the project.
- vi. Periodic verification of land allocations should be carried out to evade fraudulent allocations. The culprits involved in fraudulent land allocations should be severely punished to serve as deterrent to others and should be made to face criminal prosecution. Also, the processing of application for land allocation should be reviewed always and be adjusted to a shortest time.
- vii. Priorities in the allocation of land should be based on need, ability and readiness to develop within a specific period of time depending on the distance of the area to existing built up area. Any land that is not developed at a specific time should be revoked and reallocated to any person that is willing and ready to develop.

- viii. Public Private Partnership arrangement (PPP) either by an individual or by allottees of schemes coming together under an umbrella association should be encouraged in the development of site and services scheme. This will go a long way in reducing the infrastructure burden on the Federal Government.
- ix. Federal Government should employ more staff to fill the existing gap in manpower as a means of ensuring that its responsibilities are adequately attended to. This includes all responsibilities relating to the implementation and management of the Site and Services Programme. Also, refresher courses should be organized for officials of the schemes section to broaden their scope and knowledge and also to enhance their productivity or efficiency.
- x. The Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development should organize public enlightenment programme at reasonable intervals to keep members of the public abreast of regulation and policies regarding the Federal Site and Services Scheme. This will give the public an opportunity to air their views on implementation and planning issues on the schemes and offer advice and constructive criticism if possible.
- xi. The existing policy documents defining the role of each Department/Unit in the implementation of Site and Services Programme in the Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development should be strictly implemented and adhered to by the Management of the Federal Ministry. Where there are complaints, they should be officially channeled for review.

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